

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Golden Gate Highlands National Park, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: An annotated species list of spiders presently known from the Golden Gate Highlands National Park is provided. The checklist was compiled from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) database and museum collections. Presently, 170 species from 40 families and 116 genera are protected in the park. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (23 spp.), Thomisidae (20 spp.), and Araneidae (16 spp.) and Gnaphosidae with 14 spp., while 16 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism and conservation status for each species is provided. A large number of the species (91.6%) have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern. Approximately 7% of the total South African spider fauna is protected in Golden Gate Highlands National Park, and 29.4 % of the species recorded are South African endemics and four species are Free State Province endemics.

Keywords: South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), conservation, endemism, grassland

INTRODUCTION

In 1997 the Agricultural Research Council registered a project (DIPSA 1296) at SANParks to determine the diversity of arachnids in the different parks. This forms part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) that was initiated in 1997 with the main aim to discover, describe and make an inventory of the South African arachnid fauna (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Species distribution data are essential information needed for the conservation assessments to compile a Red Data List of the spiders of South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020) and to determine species already protected in parks and reserves.

SANParks was formed in 1926, and currently manages 20 parks covering > 3% of the total area of South Africa. In terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No 57 of 2003), the primary mandate of SANParks is to oversee the conservation of South Africa's biodiversity, landscapes and associated heritage assets through a system of national parks.

During the years several major arachnid surveys were undertaken in the national parks of which the results of 11 parks has been published (Table 1). The current study presents the results of data from the spiders sampled in the Golden Gate Highlands National Park (GGHNP) in the Free State Province (Figs 1 & 2). It includes information on the species' global distribution, endemism and conservation status.

METHODS

Study area and period: The Golden Gate Highlands National Park (GGHNP) is located in the eastern Free State (28°31'S, 28°37'E). In 1963, 47.92 km² were proclaimed as a national park. In 1981, the park was enlarged to 62.41 km² and in 1988, it was enlarged to 116.33 km². The park was joined with the neighbouring QwaQwa National Park and the amalgamation was completed in 2007, increasing the park's area to 340 km². GGHNP covers an area across the Rooiberg Mountain Range, which forms part of the greater Drakensberg–Maluti mountain system (Fig. 2). 'Golden Gate' refers to the sandstone cliffs found on either side of the valley at the Golden Gate dam in the Maluti Mountains.

The GGHNP falls within the Drakensberg World Heritage region, which boasts mixed heritage status owing to the presence of both culturally and naturally significant features (Grab *et al.*, 2011). The park is an area of rich highveld and montane grassland. It has more than 60 grass species and a large variety of bulbs and herbs. The park also has Afromontane forests and high-altitude Austro-Afro alpine grassland, which is scarce in South Africa.

Annual precipitation varies considerably across the region, but averages approximately 764 mm, of which most falls between November and April. Summer mean temperature ranges from 13 °C to 26 °C

1

2

Figures 1-2. The Golden Gate Highlands National Park (GGHNP) in the Free State Province (N. Dippenaar).

and winters temperature ranges from 1 °C to 15 °C). Frost is widespread during the winter months and snow occasionally falls on the higher peaks in the park.

Map 1. Map showing location of the Garden Route National Park.

Sampling methods and identification: Spiders were sampled during surveys undertaken by visiting arachnologists, staff of the National Museum in Bloemfontein and the Agricultural Research Institute (ARC) and students of the Free State University. Voucher specimens are housed in the National Museum in Bloemfontein and the National Collection of Arachnida at the ARC. Specimens were included in several taxonomic revisions.

Conservation status: The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020) where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range of the area of occupation was determined.

The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO. The distribution of threats across lineages was visualized using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within the categories: Data Deficient (DD), Least Concern (LC), (Table 3).

Endemicity value: The global distribution of each species was provided to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 4). Values used to indicate species endemicity (E): 6 – only known from the type locality (GGHNP); 5 – known from several localities in the Free State (FSE); 4 – known from Free State as well as an adjacent province; 3 – known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE); 2 – known from other Southern African countries (STHE); 1 – known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); 0 – also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 170 species, 115 genera, from 41 families were recorded (Tables 2 & 4). Ten species could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy was still unresolved.

Family diversity: Of the 41 spider families collected from GGHNP (Tables 2 & 4), the most species-rich families were the Salticidae (23 spp.), Thomisidae (20 spp.), Araneidae (16 spp.) and Gnaphosidae with 14 spp. There was a very high proportion of singleton families (16), that is represented by a single species only. This pattern is consistent with the faunal composition of most of the other national parks (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Spider families (FAM) and species (SPP.) recorded from some of the national parks in South Africa with references.

NATIONAL PARK	FAM	SPP.	REFERENCES 183.8
Addo	47	276	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Augrabies	29	109	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2021b
Bontebok	44	184	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2021c
Garden Route	52	245	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2024
Golden Gate	41	170	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz (in press)
Marakele	36	135	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2021a
Mountain Zebra	38	150	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lotz 2023
Karoo	38	158	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> 2024
Kruger	50	152	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003
Table Mountain	50	261	Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2024

TABLE 2. Spider diversity of the Golden Gate Highlands National Park, with total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled.

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	11	16	Philodromidae	4	7
Bemmeridae	2	2	Pholcidae	2	3
Caponiidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	2	4	Pisauridae	4	4
Clubionidae	1	2	Prodidomidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Salticidae	15	23
Deinopidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	2
Dictynidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Entypesidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	6
Eresidae	2	2	Sicariidae	1	2
Gnaphosidae	10	14	Sparassidae	2	2
Hahniidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	3	6
Hersiliidae	1	2	Theraphosidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	8	8	Theridiidae	5	7
Lycosidae	8	12	Thomisidae	10	20
Macrobunidae	2	2	Trachelidae	2	2
Miturgidae	1	1	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Orsolobidae	1	1	Uloboridae	1	1
Oxyopidae	2	5	Zodariidae	1	1
				116	170

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Golden Gate Highlands National Park.

Conservation status	No. spp.	%
Not evaluated NE	10	6.5
Data deficient DD	5	2.9
Least concern LC	154	91.6
Endemicity		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	18	10.6
1 – African endemics (AE)	64	37.6
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	47	27.6
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	22	12.9
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	5	2.9
5 – Free State endemics (FSE)	4	1.8
6 – Type locality	0	0

Endemicity: Seventeen species (10.12%) sampled at GGHP have a wide distribution wider than Africa, while 64 species (38.09%) are African endemics (AE) and 22 species (13.09%) are Southern African endemics and 31 species 18.45% are South African endemics.

Four species are Free State endemics, *Spiroctenus pilosus* Tucker, 1917 (Bemmeridae), *Ancylotrypa dreyeri* (Hewitt, 1915) (Cyrtau - cheniidae), *Smeringopus lotzi* Hubert, 2012 (Pholcidae) and *Tanzania meridionalis* Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011

GGHP are the type locality of five Salticidae species: *Heliophanus sororius* Wesolowska, 2003, *Langona lotzi* Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011, *Pseudicius maculatus* Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011, *Thyenula armata* Wesolowska, 2001 and *Thyenula oranjensis* Wesolowska, 2001. But they have a wide distribution and are not restricted to the park.

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Kilima decens (ARANEIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Neoscona moreli (ARANEIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Neoscona triangula (ARANEIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Pycnacantha tribulus (ARANEIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Cheiramiona paradisis (CHEIRACANTHIDAE) (L. Lotz)

Clubiona africana (CLUBIONIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Ancylotrypa dreyeri (CYRTAUCHENIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Hogna transvaalica (LYCOSIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Pardosa crassipalpis (LYCOSIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Gephyrota glauca (PHILODROMIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Tibellus minor (PHILODROMIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Rothus aethiopicus (PISAURIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Baryphas ahenus (SALTICIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Helafricanus debilis (SALTICIDAE) (Allen Jones)

Loxoseles parramae (SICARIIDAE) (Allen Jones)

18

Leucauge decorata (TETRAGNATHIDAE) (Allen Jones)

19

Leucauge festiva (TETRAGNATHIDAE) (Allen Jones)

20

Tetragnatha keyserlingi (TETRAGNATHIDAE) (A. Jones)

21

Harpactira hamiltoni (THERAPHOSIDAE) (Allen Jones)

22

Latrodectus renivulvatus (THERIDIIDAE) (Allen Jones)

23

Steatoda capensis (THERIDIIDAE) (Allen Jones)

24

Misumenops rubrodecoratus (THOMISIDAE) A. Jones

25

Runcinia aethiops (THOMISIDAE) (Allen Jones)

26

Runcinia erythrina (THOMISIDAE) (Allen Jones)

27

Monaeses austrinus THOMISIDAE) (Allen Jones)

28

Thomisus daradioides (THOMISIDAE) (Allen Jones)

29

Thomisus stenningi THOMISIDAE) (Allen Jones)

30

Tmarus foliatus THOMISIDAE) (Peter Webb)

31

Xysticus mulleri THOMISIDAE) (Allen Jones)

32

Uloborus plumipes (ULOBORIDAE) (Allen Jones)

TABLE 4: Spiders of Golden Gate National Park listing their endemicy (END), conservation status (CON), country endemicy (CEND). LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND	FAMILY	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE				AGELENIDAE			
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
ARANEIDAE				ARANEIDAE			
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C	<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	<i>Scotophaeus relegatus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866) (Fig. 3)	1	LC	AE	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	<i>Trichothyse africana</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus zuluensis</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE	<i>Zelotes albanicus</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863) (Fig. 4)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona rapta</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864) (Fig. 5)	1	LC	AE	HAHNIIDAE			
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781) (Fig. 6)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Tyrotama abyssus</i> Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005	2	LC	STHE
BEMMERIDAE				BEMMERIDAE			
<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC	SAE	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Spiroctenus pilosus</i> Tucker, 1917	5	DD	SAE	LINYPHIIDAE			
CAPONIIDAE				LINYPHIIDAE			
<i>Caponia hastifera</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Lockett, 1968)	1	LC	AE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE				CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE	<i>Ceratinopsis dippenaari</i> Jocqué, 1984	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	<i>Metaleptyphantes perexiguus</i> (Simon & Fage, 1922)	1	LC	AE
<i>Cheiramiona paradisis</i> Lotz, 2003 (Fig. 7)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	0	LC	C
<i>Cheiramiona regis</i> Lotz, 2003	4	LC	SAE	<i>Neriere natalensis</i> van Helsdingen, 1969	3	LC	SAE
CLUBIONIDAE				CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921 (Fig. 8)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C
<i>Clubiona bevisi</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE				CYRTAUCHENIIDAE			
<i>Ancylotrypa dreyeri</i> (Hewitt, 1915) (Fig. 9)	5	DD	SAE	<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	1	LC	AE
DEINOPIIDAE				LYCOSIDAE			
<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	<i>Allocosa aurata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
DICTYNIDAE				DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Archaeodictyna</i> sp. undetermined		NE		<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
ENTYPESIDAE				ENTYPESIDAE			
<i>Lepthercus kwazuluensis</i> Ríos-Tamayo & Lyle, 2020	3	LC	SAE	<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE
ERESIDAE				ERESIDAE			
<i>Dresserus kannemeyeri</i> Tucker, 1920	4	LC	SAE	<i>Hippasa funerea</i> Lessert, 1925	2	LC	STHE
<i>Stegodyphus tentoriicola</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898) (Fig. 10)	3	LC	SAE
GNAPHOSIDAE				GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Asemesthes lineatus</i> Purcell, 1908	1	LC	AE	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903 (Fig. 11)	2	LC	STHE
MACROBUNIDAE				MACROBUNIDAE			
				<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
				<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
				<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
				<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
				<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
				<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
				MITURGIDAE			
				<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
				<i>Pseudauximus</i> sp. (new?)		NE	
				ORSOLOBIDAE			
				<i>Parapostenus</i> sp.		NE	
				<i>Azaniobus lawrencei</i> Griswold & Platnick, 1987	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND
ORSOLOBIDAE			
<i>Azaniolobus lawrencei</i> Griswold & Platnick, 1987	2	LC	STHE
OXYOPIIDAE			
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE			
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
PHILODROMIDAE			
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966) (Fig. 12)	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE
<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919 (Fig. 13)	1	LC	AE
PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Quamtana filmeri</i> Huber, 2003	4	LC	SAE
<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Huber, 2012	5	DD	SAE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
PHYXELIDIDAE			
<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
PISAURIDAE			
<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
<i>Euprostenops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Euprostenopsis pulchella</i> Pocock 1902	2	LC	STHE
<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> Pavesi 1883 (Fig. 14)	1	LC	AE
PRODIDOMIDAE			
<i>Theuma cedri</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
SALTICIDAE			
<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 15)	1	LC	AE
<i>Dendryphantes hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	2	LC	STHE
<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901) (Fig. 16)	1	LC	AE
<i>Helafricanus hastatus</i> (Wesolowska, 1986)	1	LC	STHE
<i>Heliocapensis aberdarensis</i> (Wesolowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Heliocapensis charlesi</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Heliophanus prozyskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heliophanus sororius</i> Wesolowska, 2003 *	2	LC	STHE
<i>Langona lotzi</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Myrmarachne solitaria</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE
<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
<i>Phlegra</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
<i>Pseudicius maculatus</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	2	LC	STHE
<i>Rhene</i> sp.(undetermined)		NE	

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND
<i>Tanzania meridionalis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	5	DD	SAE
<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyenula armata</i> Wesolowska, 2001*	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thyenula oranjensis</i> Wesolowska, 2001*	3	LC	SAE
SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	1	LC	AE
<i>Scytodes drakensbergensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	4	LC	SAE
SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Anyphops barnardi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Anyphops broomi</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Anyphops karrooicus</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Anyphops lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Anyphops</i> sp.(new)		NE	
SICARIIDAE			
<i>Loxosceles parramae</i> Newlands, 1981 (Fig. 17)	4	LC	SAE
<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Olios</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Diphya simoni</i> Kauri, 1950	3	LC	SAE
<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864) (Fig. 18)	0	LC	C
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866) (Fig. 19)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C
<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C
<i>Tetragnatha keyserlingi</i> Simon, 1890 (Fig. 20)	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902 (Fig. 21)	3	LC	SAE
THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Episina bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902 (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990 (Fig. 23)	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 1 (undetermined)		NE	
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 2 (undetermined)		NE	
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3 (undetermined)		NE	
<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
THOMISIDAE			
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942 (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> (Lucas, 1846)	0	LC	C
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxytate concolor</i> (Caporiacco, 1947)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE
<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)(Fig. 23)	1	LC	AE

FAMILY	END	CON	CEND
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema vallotoni</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890 (Fig. 26)	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900 (Fig. 27)	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928 (Fig. 28)	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952 (Fig. 29)	2	LC	STHE
TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Capobula montana</i> Haddad <i>et al.</i> 2021	2	LC	STHE
TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE
ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846 (Fig. 30)	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Diores termitophagus</i> Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1992	4	DD	SAE